

Hybrid Iterative-Direct Solution Strategy for Improving the Scalability of Nuclear Waste Management Simulations

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Abstract

We report on our work aiming at enabling large-scale simulations of nuclear waste management based on a simulation software combining a finite element discretization scheme formulated on a hybrid hexahedral-tetrahedral grid, and scalable sparse linear solvers. The enabling numerical tool is a domain decomposition solution strategy for the sparse system of linear equations resulting from the spatial discretization of the underlying PDEs (Partial Differential Equations). The PDEs at hand here are the Darcy's equations. A concrete application is considered for assessing the benefits of using a domain decomposition sparse linear solution strategy as compared to the originally used approach, which is based on a more classical preconditioned iterative algorithm.

1. Introduction

This work is concerned with improving the scalability of nuclear waste management simulations performed using the TRACES software [1] TRACES (Transport of RadioActive Elements in Subsurface) is a simulation software used by ANDRA (French National Agency for Radioactive Waste Management) for phenomenological description and performance/safety assessment of the integrated disposal repositories and their geological environments. This software solved PDEs modeling groundwater flow and radionuclide transfer in (un)saturated porous media. Darcy's law and diffusivity in confined aquifer equations at one or several steady states describe groundwater flow. A central numerical kernel of a simulation with TRACES is the solution of a large sparse linear system of equations with a symmetric positive definite matrix operator in some cases. The usual strategy adopted for solving this sparse system in TRACES relies on a AMG (Algebraic MultiGrid) preconditioned CG (Conjugate Graduate) algorithm, which is numerically efficient but poorly scalable. Here, we study the possibility of enhancing the scalability properties of the TRACES software by resorting to a hybrid iterative-direct solution strategy based on domain decomposition principles. This later strategy is implemented in the MaPhyS (Massively Parallel Hybrid Solver) [2]-[3] developed at INRIA. The work presented here has potential links with the EoCoE[†] (Energy Oriented Centre of Excellence). Indeed, the leveraging of advanced scalable numerical linear algebra black-box solvers such as MaPhyS has been recently or is currently considered in several European scientific contexts. The EXA2CT[‡] and NLAFFET[§] Exascale Horizon 2020 projects are two

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such contexts that are precisely addressing this question. The later is also considered in the EoCoE** (Energy oriented Centre of Excellence) work plan. As a matter of fact, in EoCoE, MaPHyS is further extended and exploited for several application domains. In MaPHyS has been integrated in the general purpose FEM CFD code Alya developed at BSC and a scalability study will be scheduled during the first semester 2017.

2. Physical and application contexts

2.1 Brief presentation of the application partner

ANDRA is the French National Agency for Radioactive Waste Management and is in charge of long-term management of all radioactive waste. ANDRA is involved in (i) a research and development mission, in order to propose long-term safety solutions for all kinds of radioactive wastes, including long-term storage, in particular studies about the deep geological repository project for high/intermediate level long lived wastes; (ii) an industrial mission concerning, on one hand, waste acceptance criteria and control and, on the other hand, siting, construction, operation, closure and monitoring of repositories; (iii) an information mission, through the regular publication of the national inventory of radioactive materials and waste. This mission includes as well an active policy of dialogue with stakeholders both at national and local level. In particular, ANDRA is responsible of the phenomenological description and performance/safety assessment of the integrated disposal repositories and their geological environments. It provides phenomenological and conceptual description of the behaviour of each repository and geological component during operating and post-closure periods, in space and time (thermal, chemical, mechanical, hydraulic-gas, radionuclide/toxic release and transfer), including uncertainties analysis. The objective is to achieve a relevant, traceable and justified data basis on multiphysics understanding at all space and time scales, in order (i) to develop safety assessment of repositories, (ii) to contribute to choices of design concept, (iii) to contribute to monitor the repositories and their environments, and (iv) to contribute to define step by step operating of the repositories. To fulfil this objective, the Performance Assessment Department from the Research and Development Division of ANDRA and its subcontractors set up and perform many numerical simulations, involving efficient and robust methods and tools, and sound link with characterization data. The department also supports definition, development, choice and implementation of relevant simulation tools for all agency activities.

In the field of phenomenological description and performance/safety assessment, ANDRA has to perform many numerical simulations, in particular to quantify flow and solute transfer in (un)saturated porous media, from the waste package to the human being and through the repository and geological environment (see Figure 1 and Figure 2). Simulations have to take into account many physical processes, applied to different components (from the waste packages to the geological media and material (clay, concrete, iron, glass, etc.) on very large time (up to one million years) and scale (from centimetre to tens of kilometres). Simulations are based on a large data set derived from an intensive characterization program. They are complex because they require a detailed geometry, with contrasts of parameters to manage and applied to physical processes, with couplings, and non-linear equations, and are thus good candidates for Exascale capabilities. Up to now, in order to fulfil good understanding of the global system with previous peculiarities, and to get knowledge and information with both reasonable time and good accuracy, many simplifications are made, whose levels depend on the efficiency of available numerical methods and tools. In the use case considered in this paper, the involved PDEs model groundwater flow and radionuclide transfer in (un)saturated porous media. Groundwater flow is described by Darcy' law and diffusivity in confined aquifer equations at one or several steady states. Radionuclide transfer is described with advection diffusion and dispersion, with linear adsorption and radioactive decay. The corresponding sets of PDEs are linear and mixed hyperbolic-parabolic. The associated simulation tool is TRACES [1], which was initially developed by the Institute of Fluid and Solid Mechanics at the University of Strasbourg and which has undergone several methodological improvements from ANDRA during the last 10 years. The software has then evolved in the context of research and development activities conducted by ANDRA and we consider in this study the most up-to-date version of TRACES.

2.2 Overview of TRACES simulation software

TRACES (Transport of RadioACTIVE Elements in Subsurface) is a simulation software used by ANDRA (French National Agency for Radioactive Waste Management) for phenomenological description and performance/safety assessment of the integrated disposal repositories and their geological environments. This software is written in

Fortran 95. It is parallelized for distributed memory architectures using a classical SPMD strategy combining a partitioning of the underlying mesh with a message-passing programming model using the MPI standard. This software solved PDEs modeling groundwater flow and radionuclide transfer in (un)saturated porous media. Darcy's law and diffusivity in confined aquifer equations at one or several steady states describe groundwater flow. Radionuclide transfer is described with advection, diffusion and dispersion, with linear adsorption and radioactive decay. The corresponding sets of PDEs are linear and mixed hyperbolic-parabolic. Spatial discretization of 3d problems is based on a discontinuous finite element method for the advection part and mixed hybrid finite element method for the other parts, formulated on conforming, structured or unstructured grid with hexahedral elements. Time integration relies on explicit or implicit schemes and a Newton method is used for the linearization of discrete system leading to the formulation of large sparse linear systems of equations. For the solution of these systems, TRACES makes use of parallel preconditioned iterative solvers offered by the Hypra^{††} library developed by the Center for Applied Scientific Computing at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, namely CG/AMG and GMRES/AMG (i.e., Algebraic MultiGrid preconditioned Krylov iterative solvers). However, although being a very efficient preconditioner from the numerical point of view, AMG is also known to scale poorly on massively parallel systems when it comes to solver general sparse systems. In this project, we study the possibility of improving the scalability of TRACES by considering the use of an algebraic hybrid iterative-direct solver whose design is based on domain decomposition principles.

Figure 1: Computational setting of geological repository structures and its environment.

Figure 2: Example of simulation of hydraulic conditions.

^{††} <http://computation.llnl.gov/projects/hypra-scalable-linear-solvers-multigrid-methods>

3. Enabling numerical tool: domain decomposition solver

Domain decomposition methods are flexible and powerful techniques for the parallel numerical solution of systems of PDEs. They can be used as a process of distributing a computational domain among a set of interconnected processors or, for the coupling of different physical models applied in different regions of a computational domain (together with the numerical methods best adapted to each model) and, finally as a process of subdividing the solution of a large linear system resulting from the discretization of a system of PDEs into smaller problems whose solutions can be used to devise a parallel preconditioner or a parallel solver. In all cases, domain decomposition methods (1) rely on a partitioning of the computational domain into subdomains, (2) solve in parallel the local problems using a direct or iterative solver and, (3) call for an iterative procedure to collect the local solutions in order to get the global solution of the original problem. Subdomain solutions are connected by means of suitable transmission conditions at the artificial interfaces between the subdomains. The choice of these transmission conditions greatly influences the convergence rate of the domain decomposition method. One generally distinguishes three kinds of domain decomposition methods [4]:

1. Overlapping methods use a decomposition of the computational domain in overlapping pieces. The so-called Schwarz method belongs to this class. Schwarz initially introduced this method for proving the existence of a solution to a Poisson problem. In the Schwarz method applied to the numerical resolution of elliptic PDEs, the transmission conditions at artificial subdomain boundaries are simple Dirichlet conditions. Depending on the way the solution procedure is performed, the iterative process is called a Schwarz multiplicative method (the subdomains are treated sequentially) or an additive method (the subdomains are treated in parallel).
2. Non-overlapping methods are variants of the original Schwarz domain decomposition methods with no overlap between neighbouring subdomains. In order to ensure convergence of the iterative process in this case, the transmission conditions are not trivial and are generally obtained through a detailed inspection of the mathematical properties of the underlying PDE or system of PDEs.
3. Substructuring methods rely on a non-overlapping partition of the computational domain. They assume a separation of the problem unknowns in purely internal unknowns and interface ones. Then, the internal unknowns are eliminated thanks to a Schur complement technique yielding to the formulation of a problem of smaller size whose iterative resolution is generally easier. Nevertheless, each iteration of the interface solver requires the realization of a matrix/vector product with the Schur complement operator, which in turn amounts to the concurrent solution of local subproblems.

In this study we concentrate on a domain decomposition that works at the matrix operator level and combines the variants 1. and 3. in a purely algebraic way. This approach is implemented in the algebraic hybrid iterative-direct solver named MaPHyS [2]-[3].

4. MaPHyS algebraic solver

The solution of large sparse linear systems is a critical operation for many numerical simulations. To cope with the hierarchical design of modern supercomputers, hybrid solvers based on algebraic domain decomposition methods have been proposed. Among them, approaches consisting of solving the problem on the interior of the domains with a sparse direct method and the problem on their interface with a preconditioned iterative method applied to the related Schur complement have shown an attractive potential as they can combine the robustness of direct methods and the low memory footprint of iterative methods. MaPHyS (Massively Parallel Hybrid Solver) [5]-[6] is a parallel linear solver, which implements this idea. The underlying idea is to apply to general unstructured linear systems domain decomposition ideas developed for the solution of linear systems arising from PDEs. The interface problem, associated with the so-called Schur complement system, is solved using a block preconditioner with overlap between the blocks that is referred to as Algebraic Additive Schwarz. To cope with the possible lack of coarse grid mechanism that enables one to keep constant the number of iterations when the number of blocks is increased, the solver exploits two levels of parallelism (between the blocks using MPI and within the treatment of the blocks using threads). This allows exploiting a large number of cores with a moderate number of nodes, which ensures a reasonable convergence behavior. MaPHyS makes use of PaStiX (Parallel Sparse matrix package) [5] as a subdomain solver. The parallelization of PaStiX relies on a specific partitioning of the matrix blocks; the core operations in PaStiX are multithreaded allowing a second level of parallelization. PaStiX makes extensive use of highly optimized dense linear algebra kernels (e.g. BLAS kernels).

5. Numerical and performance results

5.1 Description of the test problem

The new version of the TRACES simulation software has been evaluated by considering a use case involving a realistic geological medium depicted in Figure 1. This domain contains 28 layers and covers a domain of size 600 km x 600 km x 1000 m (see Figure 3). The underlying mesh contains 5,944,891 cells and 17,858,966 faces. The whole simulation workflow consists of two steps: in a first step, one computes the steady flow conditions, i.e. the hydraulic pressure and the velocity field ; then, these flow conditions are used for the simulation of the transport of radionuclides. Here, we only consider the first phase of this workflow that amounts to solve Darcy's equation.

Figure 3: Use case for hydraulic conditions computation. Unstructured hybrid hexahedral/tetrahedral mesh with 5,944,891 cells and 17,858,966 faces (which is also the number of rows and columns of the associated sparse linear system for the pressure unknowns).

5.2 Performance results

The numerical simulations reported below have been run on the **Occigen**^{††} Bull/Atos cluster at CINES. Each node of this system is equipped with an Intel E5-2690 running at 2.6 GHz, with 24 cores on each node and 64 GB or 128 GB RAM per node.

A strong scalability assessment of two solution strategies is shown in Figure 4. The reference solution strategy is the combination CG/AMG of the Hypre library (top graph). We observe that the parallel speedup obtained when using the MaPHyS solver (bottom graph) is slightly better, thus confirming the expected behaviour. However, from the wall clock time viewpoint, the simulation based on the CG/AMG solution strategy is more than 8 times faster than the one based on the MaPHyS solver. In order to explain this result, we compare in Figure 5 the time per iteration for each solution strategy. On this graph we clearly show that the MaPHyS hybrid iterative-direct solver is faster than CG/AMG on a per iteration basis. However, with the MaPHyS solver, the number of iterations to convergence increases with the number of subdomains (here, one subdomain is assigned to one core). This numerical scalability issue with domain decomposition solvers is very well known. Appropriate strategies have been designed for symmetric positive definite systems in the form of so-called *coarse grid correction* [6]. Such a correction has been recently introduced in the MaPHyS solver, but has not been exploited for the simulations discussed here.

6. Conclusion

Thanks to the use of an algebraic hybrid iterative-direct sparse system solver based on domain decomposition principles, we have developed a new version of the TRACES simulation software with enhanced scalability properties and capabilities to address very large problems. In particular, this enhanced version of the TRACES software has been applied in the present study to the calculation of the hydraulic flow conditions of a realistic geological medium, which has been designed by ANDRA for simulation campaigns conducted in the context of

^{††} <https://www.cines.fr/en>

the evaluation of a nuclear waste landfill site. In summary, although some theoretical issues still need to be addressed for improving the numerical scalability of the algebraic MaPHyS solver (i.e. minimizing the increase of the number of iterations with the number of subdomains), the new version of the TRACES simulation software has demonstrated promising capabilities for simulating in a scalable way very large problems relevant to nuclear waste management. The work presented here is currently consolidated by ANDRA and will soon benefit from a new version of the MaPHyS solver with improved numerical scalability properties.

Figure 4: Performance results on the Occigen system at CINES. Total time on 768 cores: 2.1 sec for Hypre (PCG/AMG) and 17.6 sec for MaPHyS.

Figure 5: Performance results on the Occigen system at CINES. Time per solver iteration for Hypre (PCG/AMG) and MaPHyS.

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